

Processing and Performance of Chopped Glass Fiber Reinforced RTM Composites

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ABSTRACT

A significant obstacle to the proliferation of liquid molding processes, such as resin transfer molding (RTM) and structural reaction injection molding (SRIM), in the automotive industry has been the lack of a low cost, net shape, fully automated process to manufacture fiber preforms. The Ford Programmable Preforming Process (F3P), is a cost effective, low scrap, robotic, automated, random fiber process suitable for production volumes up to ~50k units/year. This preforming process has previously been demonstrated as capable of meeting the above requirements and is currently being used to fabricate preforms for RTM components on the Aston Martin Vanquish. While the F3P technology is in production, there are still some fundamental engineering issues that need to be investigated. Foremost of which is the influence of fiber volume fraction on both the processing and performance of RTM composites. As the F3P technology is currently being used for fabricating both Class "A" (i.e., surface critical) and structural components, a wide range of fiber volume fractions must be considered. In addition, to achieve Class "A" appearance, surface veil must be used as part of the preform to promote a resin rich surface. Thus, in this paper the influence of glass fiber and surface veil content on the processing and performance of F3P RTM composites will be discussed.

KEY WORDS: Preforming, resin transfer molding, processing, performance

INTRODUCTION

Over the past thirty years, polymer composites have become accepted in the automotive industry as an alternative material to steel for the production of exterior body panels, semi-structural and structural parts. These components can be found across the entire gamut of vehicles produced by Ford Motor Company including passenger, sports, and luxury cars, light- and medium-duty trucks, sport utility vehicles, and mini-vans. Composites provide a number of benefits relative to steel including reduced weight, parts consolidation, improved corrosion resistance, improved dent resistance, increased design/styling flexibility, and reduced capital investment.

While a variety of processes are currently employed to produce these composite components in the automotive industry, resin transfer molding (RTM) has been used to manufacture parts for niche vehicles where the volumes are low (i.e., less than 5000 units per year). For example, the Aston Martin V12 Vanquish (Figure 1) contains 27 composite components using both glass and carbon fiber which are produced by RTM.

Figure 1: Aston Martin V12 Vanquish

Since RTM was used in 1974 on the Lotus Elan [1], many advancements have been made on all aspects of the technology (i.e., materials, processing, injection equipment, tooling, etc.). Some of the most recent innovations have been in the area of preforming technologies with the development of new methods such as the Ford Programmable Preforming Process (F3P) technology [2]. The combination of F3P and RTM are currently being used to manufacture the upper cargo deck (Figure 2) and the bodysides (Figure 3) of the Aston Martin V12 Vanquish.

Figure 2: Upper Cargo Deck

Figure 3: Right Hand Bodyside

F3P is a cost effective, low scrap, robotic, automated, random fiber preforming process suitable for production volumes up to ~50k units/year. The key advantages of F3P when compared to conventional preforming methods include lower costs, greater flexibility, increased repeatability, and improved reliability. However, lower cost is the foremost advantage of this technology. F3P preforms are fabricated using the lowest cost input materials (i.e., fibers in roving form). In addition, the preforms are manufactured net-shape, which further reduces cost, as subsequent trimming operations are not necessary, therefore, no additional labor, tooling, or material waste. The repeatability of the process ensures the manufacture of quality components cycle to cycle with virtually zero scrap. Production preforming trials performed to date indicate that total material scrap rates of less than 1% are possible, which can be attributed to both the repeatability and reliability of the process.

While the F3P technology is being used in production, there are still some fundamental engineering issues that require further investigation. Foremost of which is the influence of fiber volume fraction on both the processing and performance of RTM composites. As the F3P technology is currently being employed for fabricating both Class “A” (i.e., surface critical) and structural components, a wide range of fiber volume fractions must be considered. In addition, to achieve a Class “A” appearance, surface veil must be used as part of the preform to promote a resin rich surface. Thus, in this paper the influence of fiber volume fraction within F3P glass fiber preforms on the processing and performance of both Class “A” and structural RTM composites will be discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

F3P Preform Fabrication

For this study, a series of random, chopped glass fiber preforms for both Class “A” and structural applications were manufactured via the F3P technology (Table 1). All preforms for this study were fabricated using Owens Corning glass fiber rovings with Reichhold binder used to bond the preforms. Glass fiber preforms were manufactured for in-plane permeability measurements, for preform compressibility, and for RTM.

Table 1: Class “A” and Structural F3P Preforms

Preform Type	Fiber Volume Fraction (%)	Panel Thickness (mm)	Surface Veil Areal Density, A:B Surface (g/m²)	Structural Reinforcement Fiber Areal Density (g/m²)	Total Glass Fiber Areal Density (g/m²)
Class “A”	15	3.0	150:150	852	1152
Class “A”	20	3.0	150:150	1236	1536
Class “A”	25	3.0	150:150	1620	1920
Class “A”	15	4.0	150:150	1236	1536
Class “A”	20	4.0	150:150	1748	2048
Class “A”	25	4.0	150:150	2260	2560
Structural	30	3.0	N/A	2304	2304
Structural	35	3.0	N/A	2688	2688
Structural	40	3.0	N/A	3072	3072
Structural	30	4.0	N/A	3072	3072
Structural	35	4.0	N/A	3584	3584
Structural	40	4.0	N/A	4096	4096

Due to the minimum thickness constraints within the flat plaque molding tool (3.0 mm) and the in-plane permeability rig (4.0 mm), it was necessary to manufacture preforms at equivalent fiber volume fractions for two final part thicknesses (i.e., 3.0 and 4.0 mm). The Class “A” preforms were fabricated at areal densities of 1152, 1536, and 1920 g/m² corresponding to a fiber volume fraction of 15, 20, and 25% respectively for a 3.0 mm final part thickness. Additionally, Class “A” preforms were fabricated at areal densities of 1536, 2048, and 2560 g/m² corresponding to a fiber volume fraction of 15, 20, and 25% respectively for a 4.0 mm final part thickness. The structural preforms were fabricated at areal densities of 2304, 2688, and 3072 g/m² corresponding to a fiber volume fraction of 30, 35, and 40% respectively for a 3.0 mm molded part thickness. In the same way, additional structural preforms were fabricated at areal densities of 3072, 3584, and 4096 g/m² corresponding to a fiber volume fraction of 30, 35, and 40% respectively for a 4.0 mm molded part thickness. Areal density sampling of preforms manufactured for this study indicated maximum deviations from specified of ±12% with a coefficient of variation (COV) between 4 and 7% for the particular preforms analyzed.

Permeability

The permeability of the glass fiber preforms is based on the flow of a fluid through a porous media that can be described by Darcy’s law:

$$Q = \frac{k A}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dx} \quad (1)$$

where Q is the volumetric flow rate, k is the permeability constant, A is the cross sectional area, μ is the Newtonian viscosity, and dP/dx is the pressure gradient (2). Solving for the permeability (k) gives:

$$k = \frac{Q \mu}{A \frac{dp}{dx}} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, knowing the viscosity and the cross sectional area and measuring the flow rate and pressure gradient, the permeability constant can be determined.

The permeability experiments were carried out on a rectilinear test rig for the wetted permeability only. The rig consisted of a steel base plate with a cavity for the preform and a steel top plate with a line gate at the inlet end and a line vent at the exit end. The dimensions of the cavity were 500 mm long in the flow direction by 100 mm wide by 4.0 mm thick. Nine pressure transducers (Dynisco PT422A) were aligned along the centerline of the flow with an equal spacing of 50 mm. The transducers were recessed from the face of the rig to eliminate erroneous readings during preform compression to the final cavity thickness. The fluid media was Pennzoil HD SAE 30 motor oil with a viscosity of 272 cP at the test temperature of 21°C. The oil was supplied to the rig from a pressure pot at a pressure of 6.9 bar. The weight of the oil coming out of the vent was measured with a load cell (Omega Engineering 100A-25) and the flow rate was calculated from a linear fit of the mass versus time data. When the flow of the oil reached steady state, pressure drops between the transducers were calculated along the flow direction. These eight pressure drops were used in Equation 2 to calculate the permeability at the locations between the transducers. These eight permeability values were then averaged to yield a single permeability for each experiment. Four preforms from each of the F3P preforms were cut with a die to the dimensions of the permeability rig. For the Class “A” preforms, the permeability was measured in both the 0° and the 90° directions, whereas for the structural preforms, the permeability was only measured in the 0° direction.

Compressibility

Compressibility testing was conducted on a MTS 810, servo hydraulic material test system. Compressibility specimens were cut from each preform using a 76.2 mm diameter punch and a 25 Ton hydraulic press. Each sample was then weighed using an analytical balance to an accuracy of ± 0.001 g. The MTS load frame was equipped with a ± 22 kN load cell and a ± 12.7 mm displacement card. The initial opening between the upper and lower platens was set at 10 mm. Testing was conducted to a final thickness corresponding to a fiber volume fraction of approximately 50% with a crosshead speed of 50 mm/min. A total of five samples were tested from each preform type. The instantaneous thickness was then used, along with sample mass and fiber density to calculate the fiber volume fraction throughout the test. Instantaneous load data from the load cell was obtained and, along with the sample area, used to calculate compaction pressure at a given fiber volume fraction.

Resin Transfer Molding Process

The test plaques required for the mechanical property portion of this study were molded via RTM in an instrumented, matched die, chrome-plated steel, shear edge plaque tool (457 x 457 x 3 mm). As the F3P preforms were larger than these dimensions, a steel rule die was used to cut the reinforcement from the center of the preform to the appropriate size. The preform was placed into the mold cavity, the tool was closed and then a vacuum pump was used to evacuate the mold. After the cavity was evacuated, the resin system was injected using an Aplicator RI-2 resin injection machine through a line gate located at one end of the tool.

Class "A" Panels

The Class "A" resin was an unsaturated polyester resin with low profile additive from Scott Bader. The resin was accelerated with cobalt solution and an organic peroxide from Akzo Nobel was used as a catalyst. The injection rate was 0.5 l/min and the resin was injected to a pressure of ~20-25 bar. The in mold time was 15 minutes including the injection time. The lower tool temperature was set at 95°C and the upper mold was set at 85°C. The Class "A" plaques were subsequently post-cured at 110°C \pm 3°C for two hours in a re-circulating, convection oven prior to mechanical testing.

Structural Panels

The structural resin was also an unsaturated polyester resin from Scott Bader. The resin was accelerated with a cobalt solution and an organic peroxide from Akzo Nobel was used as a catalyst. The injection rate was 0.7 l/min and the resin was injected to a pressure of ~20-25 bar. The in mold time was 15 minutes including the injection time. The lower tool temperature was set at 82°C and the upper tool was set at 80°C.

Characterization

For the structural composite panels, the weight and volume fractions of the constituent materials were determined by Loss-on-Ignition (LOI). With this technique, the sample is weighed, placed into a ceramic crucible, and then thermally exposed in a muffle furnace at 600°C for two hours. Since the resin is burned-off during a LOI experiment, the weight fraction of fibers can be calculated from the initial weight of the composite and the weight of the fibers after the thermal exposure. The fiber volume fraction can then be determined based on the weight fractions and densities of the fibers and resin. The process used to determine the composition of the Class "A" composites was similar, except that the residue from the LOI experiment was dissolved with hydrochloric acid to remove the calcium carbonate filler, rinsed with deionized water and then dried in a convection oven. By weighing the sample before acid digestion and after drying, the weight content of fiber and filler was calculated. Finally, the fiber volume fraction for the Class "A" composites can be determined based on the weight fractions and densities of the fiber, resin and filler.

Mechanical Testing

Tensile and compression tests were performed on specimens machined from the composite plaques in both the 0° and 90° directions. For the tensile tests, 216.0 x 19.1 mm strips were machined from the plaques using diamond-tipped band saw. A router was then used to create the "dogbone" specimen with a nominal gage section of 76.2 by 12.7 by 3 mm. A minimum of eight tensile tests was performed for each composite at room temperature using a screw-driven mechanical test machine (Sintech 30/G) in accord with ASTM D638. The tension samples were tested at a cross-head speed of 1.27 mm/min, and an extensometer was used to monitor the longitudinal strain within the sample. For the compression tests, 139.7 x 12.7 mm strips were machined from the plaques using a diamond-tipped band saw. The edges of the samples were then de-burred using a water-cooled polishing wheel with 180-grit silicon carbide paper. Again, a minimum of eight samples was tested for each composite at room temperature using a servo-hydraulic load frame (MTS 810) in accord with ASTM D3410. The compression samples were tested at a crosshead speed of 1.27 mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the influence of glass fiber and surface veil content on the processing and performance of F3P RTM composites was examined. The processing portion of this investigation was focused on the preform produced via the F3P technology and the in-plane permeabilities and the through-thickness compressibility of these preforms. To help in understanding the performance characteristics of the RTM composites, the gross compositions were determined. In addition, the tensile and compressive properties were measured in both the 0° and 90° directions in order to evaluate the anisotropy associated with this preform technology.

Permeability

The results of the permeability testing are shown in Figure 4. The error bars represent one standard deviation. As expected, all three sets of data show the trend of decreasing permeability with increased fiber volume fraction. The two sets of Class "A" data show that the permeability is isotropic for the F3P preforms examined. The data for the structural preforms appears to be shifted to the right of the Class "A" preforms, thereby providing the same permeability at a higher fiber volume fraction (i.e., the 25 vol% Class "A" preforms has the same permeability as the 30 vol% structural preforms). This indicates that the introduction of surface veil decreases the permeability for a given glass content.

Figure 4: F3P preform permeability

Compressibility

Preform compressibility results for both Class "A" and structural preforms are given below in Figure 5. As shown, it is no surprise that the required compaction pressure for a desired thickness (i.e., 3.0 mm) is increasing as a function of fiber volume fraction for both preform types tested. However, initially less obvious is that fact that the compressibility response of the Class "A" preforms is shifted both to the left and upward relative to the compressibility response of the structural preforms. Based upon this data, the required compaction pressure for a given fiber volume fraction is higher for Class "A" preforms than for the structural preforms which more than likely can be attributed to the surface veil layers present on the Class "A" preforms which represent a much lower fiber volume fraction thereby decreasing the thickness of and increasing the fiber volume fraction of the structural reinforcement segment. In the same way, this allows one to achieve lower overall fiber volume fractions when using Class "A" versus structural preforms. Additionally, it should be noted that both data sets exhibit exponentially increasing compaction pressure versus fiber volume fraction as shown by the curves generated using the least squares method for the range of data collected.

Figure 5: Compaction pressure versus fiber volume fraction (3.0 mm thickness)

Characterization

Insight into the influence of the glass fiber and surface veil contents on mechanical properties of the RTM composite materials cannot be accurately assessed without first determining the composition of these materials. The data produced from the LOI/acid digestion experiments was used to calculate the volume fractions of the fiber and filler (if applicable) as shown in Table 2. The resin content has not been reported because it cannot be accurately determined as all organic constituents (i.e., unsaturated polyester, styrene monomer, catalyst, inhibitor, binder and sizing on the glass fibers, etc.) are burned off during an LOI experiment. Upon inspection of Table 2, it is clear that the measured fiber volume fractions are slightly different than the proposed values; however, the variation in the data is low enough to suggest that the authors were able to manufacture the RTM composites needed to evaluate the influence of glass fiber content on mechanical properties. Some scatter in fiber volume fractions was expected based upon the areal density variations discussed in the preforming sections of this paper. With regard to the Class "A" composites, the measured filler volume fractions were essentially equivalent as the variations ranged from 2.1 to 22.2%. This variation has been attributed to the RTM process as the calcium carbonate filler can be filtered out of the resin as it flows through the preform.

Table 2: Composition of RTM composite materials

Specified Fiber Volume Fraction, %	Measured Fiber Volume Fraction, %	COV Measured Fiber Volume Fraction, %	Measured Filler Volume Fraction, %	COV Measured Filler Volume Fraction, %
15	14.5	5.5	6.8	16.3
20	21.7	2.3	7.3	2.1
25	26.7	5.9	6.4	22.2
30	31.3	2.5	N/A	N/A
35	35.8	2.3	N/A	N/A
40	40.5	6.8	N/A	N/A

Mechanical Testing

The tensile modulus, strength and strain-to-failure data for the Class “A” and structural composites are provided in Tables 3a and 3b, respectively. Additionally, the compressive strength for the Class “A” and structural composites are provided in Tables 4a and 4b, respectively. In general, it should be noted that the mechanical properties were quite consistent with the COVs being less than 10% in almost all cases and the greatest COV being 13.6% for the 90° compressive strength of the 31.3% fiber volume fraction structural composite. In addition, if the scatter in the data is taken into account, there was almost a negligible amount of anisotropy in the mechanical properties. The sole exception to this finding being the tensile data for the 40.5% structural composite where the 90° modulus and strength were much greater than those measured in the 0° direction. This could be a function of preform manufacture as the robot speed and spacing were held constant and the fiber output was increased in order to fabricate higher areal density F3P performs.

With regard to the Class “A” F3P RTM composites, examination of the data indicates that fiber volume fraction had a distinct influence on tensile properties. Specifically, as the fiber volume fraction increased, the tensile modulus, strength and strain to failure increased. On the other hand, when the scatter in the data is considered, fiber volume fraction had virtually no effect on compressive strength. This seems to be related to the observed compressive failure mode: symmetric buckling in which the skin (i.e., the outer layers of the composite that contain the surface veil) delaminates from both sides of the core (i.e., the inner layer that contains the structural reinforcement). To help understand this failure mode, cross-sections of the Class “A” composites were polished and viewed. Figure 6 contains a micrograph of a 26.6% fiber volume fraction composite that highlights the skin/core structure. In this case, the skins account for approximately 40% of the composite’s thickness (i.e., 20% on each side of the core).

Figure 6: Micrograph of F3P RTM composite ($V_f = 26.6\%$) at 25x

Fiber volume fraction also had an affect on the mechanical properties of the structural F3P RTM composites. The tensile moduli and strengths in both the 0° and 90° directions increased with increasing fiber volume fractions. A similar trend was initially found for compressive strength; however, as the fiber volume fraction was increased from the intermediate level to the highest level the strength dropped off. Microstructural analyses of the structural composites were conducted which indicated that the void content was low and that the fibers were distributed randomly and homogeneously throughout the composite. Thus, the drop off in compressive strength suggests that a limiting fiber volume fraction exists between 35.8% and 40.5% for F3P RTM structural composites where interfacial and matrix dominated properties will no longer increase and that additional mechanical testing, such as interlaminar and in-plane shear, need to be conducted.

Table 3a: Tensile properties of Class “A” F3P RTM composites

Sample Direction	Fiber Volume Fraction, %	Filler Volume Fraction, %	Tensile Modulus, GPa (COV)	Tensile Strength, MPa (COV)	Strain to Failure, % (COV)
0	14.5	6.8	7.9 (4.2%)	79 (7.9%)	1.41 (11.3%)
0	21.7	7.3	9.4 (6.2%)	103 (7.3%)	1.54 (7.1%)
0	26.7	6.4	10.4 (9.0%)	129 (5.9%)	1.77 (7.4%)
90	14.5	6.8	7.6 (8.0%)	81 (11.9%)	1.51 (4.5%)
90	21.7	7.3	8.8 (4.9%)	97 (5.6%)	1.55 (6.7%)
90	26.7	6.4	10.0 (4.0%)	123 (10.5%)	1.61 (9.1%)

Table 3b: Tensile properties of Structural F3P RTM composites

Sample Direction	Fiber Volume Fraction, %	Tensile Modulus, GPa (COV)	Tensile Strength, MPa (COV)	Strain to Failure, % (COV)
0	31.3	10.9 (3.7%)	173 (6.0%)	2.13 (6.1%)
0	35.8	13.5 (4.1%)	204 (3.4%)	2.23 (5.4%)
0	40.5	14.8 (5.9%)	207 (7.5%)	2.16 (7.5%)
90	31.3	11.8 (10.1%)	199 (6.1%)	2.43 (5.2%)
90	35.8	13.7 (3.2%)	228 (3.9%)	2.29 (5.1%)
90	40.5	16.6 (7.3%)	255 (6.2%)	2.14 (6.7%)

Table 4a: Compressive strength of Class “A” F3P RTM composites

Sample Direction	Fiber Volume Fraction, %	Filler Volume Fraction, %	Compressive Strength, MPa (COV)
0	14.5	6.8	129 (7.3%)
0	21.7	7.3	120 (6.6%)
0	26.7	6.4	135 (3.8%)
90	14.5	6.8	132 (8.3%)
90	21.7	7.3	137 (7.3%)
90	26.7	6.4	138 (5.6%)

Table 4b: Compressive strength of structural F3P RTM composites

Sample Direction	Fiber Volume Fraction, %	Compressive Strength, MPa (COV)
0	31.3	176 (5.8%)
0	35.8	186 (6.6%)
0	40.5	162 (3.8%)
90	31.3	176 (13.6%)
90	35.8	200 (5.7%)
90	40.5	199 (10.4%)

CONCLUSIONS

- The introduction of surface veil decreases the permeability for a given glass content.
- The compaction pressure for a given fiber volume fraction is higher for Class "A" preforms than for the structural preforms due to the inclusion of the surface veil.
- Filtering of the calcium carbonate filler occurred as the resin flowed through the Class "A" preforms; however, this effect had a negligible impact on the mechanical properties considered in this study.
- Fiber volume fraction had virtually no effect on the compressive strength of the Class "A" composites. This seems to be related to the observed compressive failure mode: symmetric buckling in which the skin delaminates from both sides of the core.
- The drop off in compressive strength suggests that a limiting fiber volume fraction exists between 35.8% and 40.5% for F3P RTM structural composites where interfacial and matrix dominated properties will no longer increase.

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